

Exploring the feasibility of Digital Mobility Outcomes as Clinical Trial Endpoints: A scoping review protocol

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Study Description & Rationale

In this scoping review, we aim to explore existing evidence on gait and walking parameters (GaWPs) such as gait speed, gait variability, and volume of walking to assess their potential as Digital Mobility Outcomes (DMOs), or digitally-measured outcomes of gait and mobility. This work is part of Mobilise-D, a public-private partnership sponsored by the European Union Innovative Medicines Initiative which aims to deliver, validate, and obtain regulatory approval for a suite of real-world DMOs. [1] As an early step in the Mobilise-D project, this study will hone our understanding of the contexts and purposes for which DMOs might be most effectively used as research instruments. Specifically, we aim to compile an initial body of evidence in four disease areas from which the construct validity, prognostic value, responsiveness, and investigational utility of DMOs can be explored. By mapping the literature and providing a narrative synthesis of our findings, we will identify which GaWPs pose the greatest potential if developed and formally qualified as DMOs.

The format and content of this protocol will adhere to methodological guidance on designing and reporting scoping reviews developed by Arksey and O'Malley [2] and progressed by Levac et al [3]. Study conduct and reporting will also adhere to relevant aspects of the PRISMA-P and PRISMA-ScR guidelines for scoping and systematic reviews [4,5,6].

This protocol will also be submitted for publication as a peer-reviewed protocol paper, which will provide additional context and rationale for the study.

Overall Objective

Explore the potential of DMOs as clinical trial endpoint measures by identifying, mapping, and synthesizing existing evidence on their construct validity, prognostic value, and responsiveness to intervention in five disease areas.

Research Questions

Research Question 1: What differences in gait and walking parameters have been identified between target populations and healthy controls?

a-priori hypothesis: DMOs will identify differences in gait and walking between target populations and healthy controls, including gait speed, step length, step width, and step variability.

Research Question 2: What is the evidence on the association between gait and walking parameters and clinically-relevant measurements of physical function, health-related quality of life, symptoms, and disease severity in each of the target populations?

a-priori hypothesis: DMOs will exhibit strong correlations with clinical measurements assessing physical status (i.e., PROs and functional tests of exercise capacity, strength, motor function) and weaker correlations with those assessing overall disease severity or symptoms.

Research Question 3: What is the evidence on the prognostic value of gait and walking parameters in each of the target populations?

a-priori hypothesis: DMOs will exhibit prognostic value for endpoints such as HRQoL, fall risk, healthcare costs, cognitive ability, and mortality.

Research Question 4: In which contexts and for what purposes (e.g., identify adverse events, quantify drug response, etc.) have gait and walking parameters been used as primary, secondary, or exploratory endpoints in interventional studies in each of the target populations?

a-priori hypothesis: DMOs will be used rarely as endpoints in interventional studies. When they are used, DMOs will be responsive to interventions designed to improve physical ability and motor function or reduce mobility-limiting symptoms in each of the disease areas.

Definitions

Mobility: According to the International Classification of Functioning, Disability, and Health (ICF), “mobility” is defined as moving by (a) changing body position or location or by transferring from one place to another, (b) by carrying, moving or manipulating objects, (c) by walking, running or climbing, and (d) by using various forms of transportation”. As this definition is broad, we will limit our scope to parts A and C for the purposes of this review.

Gait and Walking Parameters (GaWPs): Parameters of gait or walking which *can be, but are not necessarily, measured digitally*, including spatiotemporal parameters (i.e., gait speed, step length or width, gait variability, etc.) or ‘macro’ parameters such as walking bouts, bout duration, step count, time spent walking, etc.

Digital mobility outcome (DMO): DMOs are digitally-measured GaWPs used to assess an individual’s health status and mobility. For the purposes of this review, parameters of interest are those that *have the potential to be* measured in real-world settings by wearable sensor technologies placed on the hip or lower back.

“Clinically-relevant” measurements: For the purposes of our review, “measurements” will refer to instruments or tests that assess an aspect of a patient’s health at a single point in time. We will define “clinically-relevant” measurements and outcomes as those that are routinely and broadly used in either clinical practice or in major pharmaceutical or epidemiological studies.

“Clinically-relevant” outcomes: For the purposes of our review, “outcomes” are specific results or effects that can be measured [7]. While outcomes are often assessed through “measurements,” outcomes assess change in health status over time or following intervention. We will define “clinically-relevant” outcomes as those that are routinely and broadly used in either clinical practice or in major pharmaceutical or epidemiological studies.

Study Outputs

In this study we will map existing literature, synthesize existing evidence, and identify research gaps. We will achieve this through three primary outputs:

- A map of the literature addressing the research questions on a pre-defined list of “clinically – relevant” DMOs, measurements, and outcomes.
- A narrative synthesis of the identified evidence on each of the research questions. Comparisons may be made between technology types, measurement settings, intervention types, and disease areas.

- A gap analysis to identify areas where evidence is established, which are ready for systematic review, or where additional research is needed.

Study Eligibility Criteria

Eligibility criteria are divided into three categories:

- General eligibility criteria applying to all studies and research questions
- Research-question-specific eligibility criteria
- Disease-specific eligibility criteria

General Eligibility Criteria (All research questions)	
Populations & Patient Characteristics	<p>People having a confirmed diagnosis of one of the following conditions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Parkinson’s disease • Multiple Sclerosis • Hip Fracture • COPD <p>A “confirmed diagnosis” is defined as a diagnosis made by a professional physician based on the relevant diagnostic criteria at the time of the study’s publication. Eligibility criteria regarding age range, disease severity level or disease sub-type are disease-specific and are described in Supplement 1.</p>
DMOs	<p>A list of GaWPs adapted from three well-known factor analyses of gait (Verghese et al., 2007 [8]; Hollman et al., 2011 [9]; Lord et al., 2013 [10]) and a list of secondary DMOs prioritized by WP2 will be included in this study. These parameters are summarized below and their working definitions are available in Supplement 2.</p> <p><i>Spatial Parameters</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Step length (mean, variability, asymmetry) • Stride length (mean, variability) • Step width (mean, variability) <p><i>Temporal Parameters</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cadence (mean, variability) • Step time (mean, variability, asymmetry) • Stride time (mean, variability) • Stance time (mean, variability, asymmetry) • Swing time (mean, variability, asymmetry) • Single support time (mean, variability, asymmetry) • Double support time (mean, variability) <p><i>Spatiotemporal parameters</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gait speed (mean, variability) • Stride speed (mean, variability) <p><i>Daily Volume of Walking</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Walking time • Step Count • Number and/or duration of walking bouts

Technology Type	<p>GaWPs should be measured by at least one of the following technologies:</p> <p>Stopwatch (gait speed only), speed gates, Accelerometer, gyroscope, magnetometer, inertial measurement units (IMU), instrumented/electronic walkways or mats, force plates, optometric gait assessment systems, video-based gait assessment system, radio signal-based gait assessment system, pressure sensors or insoles, mobile phone-based accelerometers, gyroscopes, or magnetometers</p> <p>GPS and barometer will be included if it supplements the measurement of a technology above.</p> <p>Any number, placement (wrist, lower back, ankle, etc.), or configuration of sensors will be included.</p> <p>Step count measured by pedometers will be excluded due to their limited validity in the target populations.</p>
Setting	<p>Supervised, semi-supervised, or unsupervised measurements of gait and walking parameters made during research studies in laboratory settings, in-clinic (inpatient or outpatient), or under free-living conditions will be included.</p>
Walking Activity & Conditions	<p>GaWPs can be measured during continuous walking, straight walking, curvilinear walking, or a mix of these.</p> <p>Single-task, double-task, straight, curvilinear walking, walking with or without turns, and with or without obstacle avoidance are included.</p> <p>Measurements during select clinical gait speed tests will be included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4m, 5m, 10m, 30m walk test, timed 25 foot walk, or other short fixed-distance walking test • 2 Minute walk test <p>Conditionally Include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <u>Timed Up and Go:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Include if walking speed is measured via an accelerometer or other digital measure during the walking phase, exclude otherwise • <u>Treadmill Walking:</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Fixed-Speed Treadmill: INCLUDE any GaWP EXCEPT gait speed ○ Self-Adjusting Speed Treadmill: INCLUDE any GaWP • <u>6Minute WT, 12Minute WT, 400m WT, (or other long walking tests):</u> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Non-Instrumented Test: EXCLUDE ○ Instrumented test: INCLUDE any GaWP EXCEPT gait speed <p>Exclude:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 -12 Minute Walk Test or longer walking test • Maximum distance walked • Incremental shuttle walk test • Endurance shuttle walk test • Tandem walking, wide step walking, backward walking, or other <i>intentional</i> non-natural walking or purposefully altering gait (e.g., instructions to concentrate on lifting toes) • Self-reported step count or walking time

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Other walk tests that artificially alter step time or gait parameters, such as stepping in time to a beat or music or consciously altering gait mechanics • Walking during gait training, including virtual reality and other gait training interventions • GaWPs measured specifically during turning, gait initiation, gait termination, stair climbing, response to sudden stimulus or push, single steps, other specific subsets of walking tasks <p>Any testing speed (e.g., self-selected vs. maximum speed) and start conditions (e.g., static start or rolling start) will be included.</p> <p>Analysis on any bout length or walking distance (aside from the exclusions on clinical gait speed tests, above) will be included.</p>
Geographic Region/Location	Any
Language of Publication	English abstract available Full text available in English, German, Spanish, French, Italian, Dutch, Norwegian, Hebrew, Catalan, and any other languages spoken within the Mobilise-D consortium
Publication status/type	<p>Include</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Published, peer-reviewed studies • Gray literature (reports, policy documents, PhD theses) • Conference abstracts (if sufficient information to address a research question is reported) • Study protocols for controlled trials using GaWPs as outcomes will be indexed, but not included in the final analysis <p>Exclude</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Master's theses • Protocols and clinical trial registrations with no original results (with the exception above) • Editorials and letters to the editor • Review papers
Publication time frame	20 years (1999-2019) Based on recommendations from subject matter experts, reflecting advances in technology in the late 1990s and early 2000s.

Research Question 1: Eligibility Criteria

DMO Usage	The differences between at least one target population and healthy controls are studied using DMOs
Study Types & Analyses to Include	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Case-control studies - Cross-sectional studies - Cross-sectional analyses in longitudinal studies - Exclude: single case studies or case series (i.e., multiple case studies presented together)

Minimum data set/sample size	At least 10 patients or participants per arm included in the final analysis
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Research Question 2: Eligibility Criteria	
DMO Usage	<p>The relationship between at least one DMO and at least one clinically-relevant measurement is studied in a target population</p> <p>Studies exploring the relationship between two in-clinic walking distance/speed tests (e.g., between distance/speed during the 6MWT and time/speed in the T25FW) will be excluded. Correlations between walking speed measured during clinical tests and other types of tests (e.g., UPDRS, HR-QoL assessments) will be included.</p>
Clinically-relevant measurements	<p>Clinically-relevant, validated instruments or tests will be included if they assess at least one of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disease Severity & Symptoms - Relevant physiological measurements - Functional Status (e.g., Ability to perform activities of daily living) - Health-Related Quality of Life - Mental Health (e.g., Depression and Anxiety) - Cognition - Physical Function, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Walking or other functional assessments o Motor Function (e.g., Balance, fine and gross motor function, tremor, fall risk, etc.) o Functional & Maximal Exercise Capacity o Strength o Fatigue - Other relevant disease-specific factors <p>Through at least one of the following assessment types:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Patient reported outcome measures (e.g., EQ5D or VAS for health-related quality of life) - Subjective clinical assessments (scored or assessed by a trained observer – e.g., UPDRS, EDSS, etc.), - Objectively-measured clinical assessments (e.g., assessed via technology, timed test, etc.) - Home-based assessments - Physiological measurements that assess function or disease severity (e.g., number and size of lesions in MS, ejection fraction in CHF, FEV1 in COPD) <p>A pre-defined list of broadly-used disease-agnostic and disease-specific measurements will be included. This list was defined in consultation with the research team and is provided in Supplement 5.</p> <p>If the instrument or test used to make assessments is not reported, the study will be excluded. Correlations to symptoms/reports of symptoms without reporting a validated instrument for measuring those symptoms will also be excluded.</p>

Study Types & Analyses to Include	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cross-sectional studies - Cross-sectional analyses in longitudinal studies - Exclude: single case studies or case series (i.e., multiple case studies presented together)
Duration/Follow-up	<p>Data is collected and analysis is conducted based on a single time point (i.e., cross-sectional analysis).</p> <p>If studies are longitudinal, only analyses conducted at a single point are included in RQ2 (for example, correlation between gait speed and the Berg Balance Scale at baseline)</p>
Minimum data set/sample size	At least 10 patients included in the final analysis

Research Question 3: Eligibility Criteria

DMO usage	The relationship between at least one DMO and at least one clinically-relevant outcome is studied in a target population
Clinically-relevant outcomes	<p>Studies will be included if they assess the relationship between an included DMO and least one of the following outcomes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disease/Disability Status or Progression - Health-Related Quality of Life - Mortality - Healthcare Utilization (e.g., hospitalizations, readmissions, home care, costs, invasive procedures, etc.) - Physical Function (e.g., exercise capacity, motor function, balance, strength) - Functional Status (e.g., activities of daily living) - Fatigue - Cognition - Mental Health (e.g., depression, anxiety, apathy) - Falls - Life Space - Residential Status - Use of Mobility Aids - Disease-specific outcomes such as exacerbations (COPD), relapses (MS) or decompensation (CHF) <p>A detailed list of included outcome measurements was defined a-priori in consultation with the research team and is provided in Supplement 6. Any relevant method of assessing the outcomes of interest will be included in the review. (e.g., for mortality, both 1-year mortality and 5-year mortality will be included in the review). Outcomes outside of the categories included on this list will be excluded from the review.</p>
Study Types	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cohort studies - Longitudinal studies - Longitudinal analysis of a control arm of a randomized controlled trial
Analyses	Study reports multivariate analyses, prediction models, or machine learning analyses with the following minimum criteria:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At least age, sex, and disease severity are included as covariates or otherwise adjusted for (the reason being that any measurement requiring some effort to measure (like a DMO) needs to add to very easily available information for predicting outcomes. Univariate predictions by just a DMO would not be meaningful) - At least 20 recorded events of an outcome of interest. In this case, we can interpret ‘event’ as “by the end of the study, how many times did outcome X occur?” ‘Events’ are independent of the number of patients included in the study. Rather, they describe how many patients experienced an outcome of interest. For example, if the prediction model was designed to predict falls, but the dataset used to develop the model only included 15 falls, it would not pass our criteria even if the study included 1,000 patients. <p>Reports of prediction models at any level of maturity will be included (e.g., model development, validation, etc.)</p> <p>If a study meets these criteria for any single outcome of interest, the outcome will be included in the review. Other outcomes reported in the same paper that do not meet these criteria (e.g., too few events) will not be included in the review.</p> <p>Models based on machine learning will be included even if the minimum number of co-variates and events are not reported, as this information is not always available for such models.</p> <p>Relevant information may include (but are not limited to):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adjusted odds ratios, risk ratios, hazard ratios • Impact of a DMO on the relative likelihood of an event to occur • Impact of DMO on predictive model’s sensitivity, specificity, ROC analysis, or similar • Impact of DMO on machine learning model’s sensitivity, specificity, ROC analysis, or similar <p>Exclude: Univariate analyses, models excluding age, sex, or disease severity, models based on less than 20 recorded events of the outcome of interest</p>
Duration/Follow-up	Study reports at least two measurements: the DMO at baseline and a clinically-relevant outcome measure at the end of the study. Studies will not be excluded on the basis of duration or follow-up frequency, as long as a longitudinal analysis is conducted.

Research Question 4: Eligibility Criteria

DMO usage	A DMO is used as a primary, secondary, or exploratory outcome in an interventional study in a target population
Study Aims	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - To test efficacy/effectiveness of an intervention via DMOs in target populations - To test safety of an intervention via DMOs in target populations

Study Types	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Randomized Controlled Trials - Non-randomized controlled interventional trials - Published protocols of interventional trials (indexed, not analyzed) - Exclude: Uncontrolled interventional studies
Intervention type	Any type of drug and non-drug intervention
Duration/Follow-up	Study reports at least two measurements: the DMO at baseline at the end of the study (or at least one follow-up in the case of RCTs). Studies will not be excluded on the basis of duration or follow-up time.
Minimum data set/sample size	At least 10 patients per study arm included in final analysis

Information Sources

The following sources will be searched to identify relevant studies, though this list may be amended in consultation with an information specialist:

- Peer-reviewed literature: MEDLINE, CINAHL, Scopus, Web of Science, Embase, IEEE Digital Library, and the Cochrane library. Additional databases may be added following consultation with an information specialist.
- Gray literature (reports, conference abstracts, theses, etc.): ACM Digital Library, ProQuest Dissertations, Open Grey, and the National Information Center’s Health Services Research Projects in Progress Database
- Additional sources will include manual searches of reference lists from relevant studies as well as publications from the review team’s private libraries
- Studies registered on clinicaltrials.gov
- Google Scholar: The first 100 search results will be screened for relevant articles in two sorting configurations: by relevance and by date.
- The review team will contact studies’ corresponding authors for additional information as necessary

Search Strategy

To ensure an appropriate search strategy, search terms, syntax, and information sources will be selected in consultation with an experienced information specialist and subject-matter experts. Search strings will include terms associated with the target populations and included DMOs in the following structure: (gait terms) AND (disease area terms) AND (publication years).

The following search string was developed for EMBASE by an experienced information specialist in consultation with the research team and will be replicated for other included databases:

String No.	Query	Results
#1 (Gait terms)	(((step* OR stride*) NEAR/2 (speed OR velocit* OR time* OR length* OR width* OR frequenc* OR rate* OR rhythm* OR variabilit* OR symmetr* OR asymmetr* OR count* OR number* OR distance* OR cadence*)):ti,ab) OR (((swing* OR stance* OR 'single support' OR 'double support') NEAR/2 (time* OR duration* OR variabilit* OR symmetr* OR asymmetr*)):ti,ab) OR (((spatiotemporal OR 'spatio-temporal') NEAR/2 (parameter* OR feature* OR characteristic*)):ti,ab) OR (((gait OR walk* OR ambulat*) NEAR/2 (speed OR velocit* OR time* OR cadence* OR pace* OR rhythm* OR	

	volume* OR bout* OR duration* OR distance* OR intensit* OR variabilit* OR asymmetr* OR symmetr* OR parameter* OR feature* OR characteristic* OR assess* OR examin* OR analys* OR batter* OR measure* OR test*)):ti,ab)	
#3 (Disease- area terms)	'chronic obstructive lung disease'/exp OR 'Parkinson disease'/exp OR 'parkinsonism'/exp OR 'multiple sclerosis'/exp OR 'demyelinating disease'/exp OR 'hip fracture'/exp OR (((chronic OR lung OR pulmonary OR respirat* OR airway* OR airflow*) NEAR/3 obstruct*) OR copd):ti,ab OR (parkinson* OR 'paralysis agitans'):ti,ab OR (((multipl* OR disseminated OR insular) NEAR/3 scleros*) OR 'chariot disease' OR demyelinat*):ti,ab OR ((hip* OR femur* OR femoral OR trochant* OR pertrochant* OR intertrochant* OR subtrochant* OR intracapsular* OR extracapsular*) NEAR/5 fracture*):ti,ab	
#3 (Publication years)	[1999-2019]/py	
#4 (Final)	#1 AND #2 AND #3	

Study Selection

Process & Record-Keeping

Review records will be kept in a specialized software designed for scoping reviews (DistillerSR). The software will facilitate the compilation and storage of abstracts, full-text publications, data extraction forms, and coding frames. Records of duplicate exclusion, study eligibility, and individual author contributions will also be managed by the software.

Duplicate studies will be identified by comparing titles, authors, publication years, and (if necessary) abstracts prior to screening from inclusion. Duplicates will be removed from the list of articles to be screened. If duplicates are identified during full text review or data extraction, the duplicate will be excluded and its reason for exclusion noted. Multiple sources reporting on the same study will be linked and analyzed as one study in the review.

Preparation & Piloting

- All reviewers will have subject matter expertise in the target population of their review and will receive training on systematic review conduct. Information specialists, subject matter experts, and other stakeholders will be consulted to ensure search strategy is appropriate and comprehensive.
- Search results from all sources will be compiled and duplicate publications removed.
- Study eligibility criteria will be piloted on a random set of studies (50 abstracts and 15 full-text articles) identified during previous searches to ensure sensitivity and mutual understanding between the reviewers. Adjustments and clarifications will be made to eligibility criteria as necessary during this stage.

Phase 1: Title & Abstract Review

- Two reviewers will independently screen each title and abstract for inclusion for full text review according to pre-defined eligibility criteria. Following the screening, reviewers will combine and compare their lists.

- We anticipate that disease-specific knowledge will be necessary for full-text eligibility assessment, data extraction, and synthesis. Thus, included studies will be segmented by disease area through a triage form during the screening process to ensure full-text review by team members with disease-specific knowledge.
- In the case of disagreement on an abstract's eligibility, the paper will be included in the full-text review if deemed potentially relevant by at least one reviewer.
- The authors may add additional rounds of abstract screening for additional eligibility criteria if they are identified during the study process, or if disease-specific knowledge is required to make inclusion/exclusion decisions. Additional rounds would follow the same procedure as the original abstract review step.

Phase 2: Full-Text Review

- Two reviewers will independently assess each full-text article for inclusion according to pre-defined eligibility criteria for each research question. Eligibility for each research question or reason(s) for exclusion will be documented. Cohen's Kappa (or Fleiss' Kappa if more than two raters) will be conducted to assess inter-rater variability.
- During the full-text review process, articles deemed eligible by each reviewer will be further 'triaged' to assess relevance for each research question. During formal data extraction, custom decision logic built into the DistillerSR software will match relevant forms to each included article based on these data items.
- The reviewers will combine their lists of eligible studies and disagreements will be resolved through discussion between the reviewers. If no consensus can be reached, a third reviewer will review the full-text article and make the final determination.

Addressing Unforeseen Eligibility Criteria

- If previously unspecified DMOs, measurements, or outcomes are identified during the review process which may be relevant to the review, the measurement or outcome will be submitted to a committee of project leads and subject matter experts to decide whether and how to adjust eligibility criteria. If included, the adjusted eligibility criteria will be applied to all studies, including previously screened studies and reported in the reports and publications.

Data Extraction & Charting

Phase 1: Form Development

- Pre-defined data collection forms will be developed through an iterative review process with the research team and further expert feedback. The form will be designed to capture all relevant study data and contextual information while ensuring adequate flexibility to capture emerging trends. The number and complexity of data items to be extracted may be adjusted based on the number of full texts included in the review.
- Prior to formal initiation of the data extraction process, the forms will be tested by reviewers on a random sample of five studies. Additional modifications or improvements identified through this process will be reviewed and approved by the research team.

Phase 2: Data Extraction

- Data extraction from each article will be conducted independently by two reviewers according to a pre-defined data extraction form.
- During the screening process, articles will be 'triaged' to assess relevance for each research question and disease area. During formal data extraction, custom decision logic built into the DistillerSR software will match relevant forms to each included article based on these data items. Further data will then be extracted according to pre-defined forms.

- Studies' corresponding authors will be contacted if clarification, confirmation, or additional information is required.
- Following the completion of data extraction, the reviewers' final data sets will be compared. Inconsistencies or disagreements will be resolved through discussion. If no consensus can be reached, a third, senior member of the research team will be consulted.

Adding or Adapting Data Items

- If previously unspecified data items are identified during the review process which may be relevant to the review, the measurement or outcome will be submitted to a committee of project leads and subject matter experts to decide whether and how to adjust the data extraction form. If included, the new data items will be extracted from all included studies.

Preliminary Data Items

Data Items	Associated Questions
Publication Details (All research questions)	
Authors & Affiliations	Who conducted the research?
Type	In what type of literature was the study published? (Journal, grey literature, conference abstract, etc.)
Year	When was the study published?
Country/Region	In which geographic region(s) did the study take place?
General Details (All research questions)	
Study Design	What was the study's design?
Study Aims	What were the study's aims?
Population	What population was studied? Were there any specific inclusion/exclusion criteria such as disease severity, subtype, or age?
Study Size	How many people participated in the study?
Included DMOs	Which DMOs were measured? How and in what setting were the DMOs measured?
Research Question 1	
Study Design	Were patients and controls matched or are the groups comparable with respect to appropriate criteria (height, age, sex, etc.)? Was gait analysis controlled for gait speed? Did the study focus on a specific subgroup or population?
Differences in DMOs	What differences in DMOs occurred (or did not occur) between target populations and healthy controls? Did these differences reach statistical significance?
Research Question 2	
Analytical Methods	How did the authors measure the relationship between clinically-relevant measurements and DMOs? What association measure was used?
Clinically-Relevant Measurement	What clinically-relevant measurements were studied?
Relationship Strength	What was the strength of the reported relationship between the measurement and the DMO? Was the association statistically significant?
Research Question 3	
Model Description	Does the study report a multivariate analysis, a prediction model, a model based on machine-learning, etc.? Which co-variates were included in the model? Which analytical methods were used?

Clinically-Relevant Outcomes	What clinically-relevant outcomes were studied to assess the DMO's prognostic value?
Prognostic Value	Did the DMO provide prognostic value with respect to the studied outcome?
Research Question 4	
Intervention type	What intervention was studied?
Study Endpoints	Was the DMO used as a primary, secondary, or exploratory endpoint? What other primary, secondary, and exploratory endpoints were measured?
Success	Was there a change in the primary endpoint between groups?
Ability to Detect Change	Was the DMO able to detect a change due to the intervention (if a change occurred)?

Collating, Summarizing, and Reporting the Results

- The body of literature included in the review will be summarized, including the types, years, distribution, DMOs, outcomes, and measurements studied in included manuscripts. A map of existing evidence will be developed for each disease area and research question, enabling identification of evidence gaps.
- Key findings for each of the three research questions will be addressed through narrative synthesis and/or frequency analysis. Findings will be compiled in tables and figures where appropriate. If possible, narrative synthesis will also be used to make comparisons and describe existing evidence within populations, across populations, and between DMO measurement settings.
- Reporting will adhere to the PRISMA-P reporting guidelines for scoping review protocols [6] with the exception of risk of bias and evidence strength assessments, which are not required for scoping reviews [2,3]

Patient and Public Involvement

- Industry partners (EFPIA representatives)
- Mobilise-D Patient advisory board
- Mobilise-D Scientific advisory board

Supplementary files

- Supplement 1: Population definitions and disease-specific eligibility criteria
- Supplement 2: Gait and walking parameters included in this review
- Supplement 3: Clinically-relevant measurements included in Research Question 2
- Supplement 4: Clinically-relevant outcomes included in Research Question 3

Study Team

Additional team members will be added as the study progresses.

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